

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) shelx

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: shelx

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0049 A Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=14.4546(3) b=17.0531(4) c=11.0345(2)
 alpha=90 beta=97.932(2) gamma=90

Temperature: 150 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	2693.94(10)	2693.93(10)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C18 H34 N6 O2, 2(C1 O4), 2(H2 O)	?
Sum formula	C18 H38 Cl2 N6 O12	C18 H38 Cl2 N6 O12
Mr	601.44	601.44
Dx, g cm-3	1.483	1.483
Z	4	4
Mu (mm-1)	2.793	2.793
F000	1272.0	1272.0
F000'	1279.13	
h,k,lmax	17,20,13	17,20,13
Nref	5175	4991
Tmin,Tmax	0.537,0.756	0.541,1.000
Tmin'	0.412	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.541 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.964 Theta(max)= 70.666

R(reflections)= 0.0562(3362) wR2(reflections)= 0.1826(4991)

S = 1.048 Npar= 359

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for N1 --N2 .	5.5 s.u.
PLAT244_ALERT_4_C	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C12 Check
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.00492 Ang.
PLAT790_ALERT_4_C	Centre of Gravity not Within Unit Cell: Resd. #	1 Note
	C18 H34 N6 O2	
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	2.729 Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	56 Report
PLAT934_ALERT_3_C	Number of (Iobs-Icalc)/SigmaW > 10 Outliers	1 Check
PLAT978_ALERT_2_C	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.	0 Info

● **Alert level G**

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms	2 Report
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1	109.8 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O2	109.6 Degree
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G	Short Inter X...Y Contact O11 ..C10	2.93 Ang.
	1-x,-y,-z =	3_655 Check
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G	Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels	4 Note
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G	Centre of Gravity not Within Unit Cell: Resd. #	5 Note
	H2 O	
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).	1 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	128 Note

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
8 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
8 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
5 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
5 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
5 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 03/05/2019; check.def file version of 29/04/2019

